

REPORT WITH DESCRIPTION OF SOURCE APPORTIONMENT SERVICE

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1 Abstract /publishable summary

Within the AQ-WATCH project, a user driven operational source apportionment service has been set-up providing information on the main sources (both sector and source regions) contributing to concentrations of nitrogen Dioxide (NO₂), particulate matter (PM) and carbon monoxide (CO). The service has been set-up for two of the three focus regions in AQ-watch, namely the Colorado Northern Front Range in the USA, and the region around Santiago de Chile. This report outlines the set-up of the source apportionment service, the status of model operation and evaluation.

The operational service is currently based on the LOTOS-EUROS (PM, NO₂) and the WRF-CHEM (CO) models using tagging techniques and driven by the most recent year of the CAMS global emission inventory as provided by CNRS and the US NEI emission inventory, respectively. In the upcoming year the aim is to refine the service for NO₂ and PM with national emission information and to extend the service to sulphur dioxide (SO₂). Evaluation of the use of national emission information has been started based on two test periods in 2016. In the last year of the project special attention will also be given to the role of agricultural emissions. Agriculture is a major contributor to air pollution, but its contribution is not widely acknowledged and potentially underestimated. An assessment on the agricultural contribution to PM episodes in Colorado and Chile will be performed and directions for further assessment of this contribution will be given. These results will be reported in the updated version of this document.

2 Conclusion & Results

With this deliverable we achieved the following results:

- Daily operational service with identification of main source sectors and regions responsible for NO₂ and PM air pollution in Santiago de Chile and the Colorado Northern Front Range over the past 6 weeks complimented by a forecast for the next 2 days.
- Operational service with identification of main sources and regions responsible for CO air pollution in the Colorado Northern Front Range over the past 6 weeks complimented by a forecast for the next 2 days.

3 Project objectives

This deliverable contributes directly and indirectly to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of the Action:

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
[1] To design and produce new global and regional air pollution atlases that include the climatological distribution of chemical pollutants complemented by quantities such as the diurnal and seasonal variations,	No

air quality and related health indices, premature mortality exceedance frequency, long-term trends, etc.	
[2] To develop software packages with the capability to provide more accurate daily forecasts of air quality at the regional scale including tailored high-resolution fire smoke and wind-blown dust forecasts; downscaling of air quality forecasts to 2 km resolution in urban areas.	No
[3] To develop a source apportionment service to mitigate air pollution and hence increase the life expectancy of the population in different regions of the world, with special focus on the role of agricultural sources of air pollution and the potentially important effects of fracking operations.	Yes
[4] To develop a new tool-box that will be user-friendly and accessible to decision-makers to evaluate the efficiency of proposed mitigation measures in different industrial sectors on the resulting level of air pollutants in three different regions of the world. This will establish the basis for their wider adoption and generalization.	Yes
[5] To co-design, co-produce and co-evaluate for the first time prototype products and services with prime users in three regions of the world chosen for their specific level of economic, social and environmental development.	Yes

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package.

Objectives of WP4	Relevance in this deliverable?
4.1 To establish a user driven service for (NRT) source apportionment information	Yes
4.2 To establish a user driven service for mitigation information on most effective emission reduction measures	Yes
4.3 To establish a fracking service for the assessment of the impact of fracking activities on air pollution	No
4.4 To improve the quality of the above mentioned three services, through validation, customization and targeted developments	Yes

4 Detailed report on the deliverable

4.1 General description of source attribution service

Within the AQ-watch project, several services are set-up that provide information on the past, current and future (next 2-3 days) air quality situation in the world and specifically for the three target regions (Santiago de Chile, Colorado Northern Front Range and Beijing). The aim of this work package is to go a step further by providing insight in the dominant source sectors and regions responsible for (high) levels of air pollution. This information is crucial to support the design of effective mitigation strategies for improving air quality and, hence, public health in the target regions.

For the service two different air quality models with their individual source attribution techniques are applied to provide source attribution information for two target regions: Santiago de Chile and the Colorado Northern Front Range. The models and their tagging systems are described in sections 4.3.1, 4.3.2, 4.4.1 and 4.4.2. The systems are in general transferable to any other region with the side note that the quality of the results is depending on the quality of the available information used as input to the systems, e.g. emissions and their distribution in time and space, meteorological data and land use information.

	South America- Chile- Santiago	CONUS- Colorado Northern Front Range
LOTOS-EUROS	PM, NO ₂	PM, NO ₂
WRF-CHEM	CO	CO

The regions and species targeted by each of the models are summarised in Table 1.

	South America- Chile- Santiago	CONUS- Colorado Northern Front Range
LOTOS-EUROS	PM, NO ₂	PM, NO ₂
WRF-CHEM	CO	CO

Table 1: Overview of models used, and regions and species targeted by current operational source attribution service

Figure 1 shows an example of what the attribution service will look like, with the attribution to regions in the top plot and attribution to source sectors in the bottom plot. Although the service is running operationally, the real data from the operational data streams has not yet been included in the AQ-watch interface. In the following sections the emission input and set-up of the source apportionment systems are presented.

Figure 1: Example of attribution service in the AQ-watch interface (no real data yet)

4.2 Emissions

The source attribution services are based on chemistry transport models which are dependent on information on the emissions from different sources within the domains of interest. Below we provide short descriptions of the different emission inventories used or planned to be used within the service.

4.2.1 CAMS-glob-ant v4.2

The CAMS global anthropogenic emissions (Granier et al., 2019) are based on the EDGARv4.3.2 inventory developed by the European Joint Center (JRC, Crippa et al., 2018) and the CEDS emissions (Hoesly et al., 2018) which provide historical emissions for the 6th IPCC Assessment Report (AR6). The inventory contains emission data for 12 different sectors. Monthly emission profiles provided by CAMS-GLOB-TEMPO (Guevara et al., 2021) are applied to the annual emissions from EDGARv4.3.2 for the years 2000-2012. After 2012, the data are linearly extrapolated to 2020 using trends derived from the CEDS emissions for the years 2011-2014. The weekly and hourly emission profiles must be supplied by the model itself.

4.2.2 CAMS-global v4.2 + Chilean emissions for residential combustion

For Chile, local information on emissions is available. In the work presented here we performed some runs with an emission inventory where the CAMS-global residential combustion emissions have been replaced by local emissions. This is an intermediate step towards the use of the inventory described in the next section.

4.2.3 CAMS-global v4.2 + INEMA v1.0 for Chile

For Chile, a gridded national inventory of anthropogenic emissions (INEMA_v1.0) based on local information is available and provided by the partners of university de Chile (Álamos et al., 2021). The INEMA_v1.0 dataset includes annual emissions for vehicular, industrial, mining, energy and residential sectors for the period 2015–2017 and spatially distributed onto a high-resolution grid (1 × 1 km approximately). These emissions have been combined by BSC with the CAMS-GLOB-ANT_v4.2 emissions using the HERMESv3_GR emission processing system (Guevara et al., 2019) to produce a daily, vertically distributed and speciated inventory for all sectors for the outermost LOTOS-EUROS South America domain (Figure 3). INEMA_v1.0 emissions were regridded onto the final working domain following a mass conservative approach, while original CAMS-GLOB-ANT_v4.2 emissions reported for Chile were masked out. The annual emissions reported by INEMA_v1.0 were disaggregated to a daily resolution for the months of January and July 2016 making use of the CAMS-GLOB-TEMPO_v3.1 temporal profiles (Guevara et al., 2021), which are based on national information including electricity production statistics reported by CNE (2021) and congestion statistics provided by TomTom (https://www.tomtom.com/en_gb/traffic-index/). Emissions from the industrial and energy sectors were vertically distributed using the TNO sector-dependent profiles, which are derived from Bieser et al. (2011). The following assumptions had to be made during the combination of the two emission datasets:

- For the energy and industry sectors, INEMA do not report CH₄, so for Chile we used the emissions reported by CAMS-GLOB-ANTv4.2

- For the road transport sector INEMA do not report SO_2 nor NH_3 emissions, so for Chile we used the emissions reported by CAMS-GLOB-ANTv4.2
- We assumed that the VOCs reported for energy and industry are equal to NMVOC as INEMA do not report CH_4 emissions neither NMVOC.
- It is assumed that reported NO_x emissions are expressed as NO_2 (to do conversion from mass to mole) since it is not known in which unit the emissions estimated by the RETC (Industry, Energy & Mining) are expressed. This also holds for the residential sector where the documentation on the emission factors does not specify this.

Figure 2 shows a comparison between the residential combustion primary elemental carbon (PEC) emissions reported by the CAMS-GLOB-ANT_v4.2 (top) and the INEMA_v1.0 (bottom) inventories for the 15th July 2016 in Chile. Large differences are observed in terms of total and spatial distribution of the emissions. CAMS-GLOB-ANT_v4.2 tends to allocate more emissions in the main urban areas (Santiago de Chile), while INEMA reports more emissions in rural areas. These discrepancies were already reported by Huneus et al., (2020).

Figure 2: Emission maps of primary elemental carbon (PEC) [$\text{kg}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$] for the 15th July 2016, from residential combustion activities reported by CAMS-GLOB-ANTv4.2 and INEMA_v1.0

4.2.4 US NEI emissions

The National Emissions Inventory (NEI) is a detailed estimate of air emissions that include criteria pollutants and hazardous air pollutants. The NEI is released every three years based primarily upon data provided by State, Local, and Tribal air agencies for sources in their jurisdictions and supplemented by data developed by the US EPA. The NEI is built using the Emissions Inventory System (EIS) first to collect the data from State, Local, and Tribal air agencies and then to blend that data with other data sources.

The U.S. National Emission Inventory (NEI) 2017, which provides speciated gas phase and aerosol emissions for 2017 has become available in 2020. Information on the inventory including technical documentation, reports and summaries is available from the U.S. EPA website (<https://www.epa.gov/air-emissions-inventories/2017-national-emissions-inventory-nei-data>).

Typically, the use of NEI emissions requires running the complex Sparse Matrix Operator Kernel Emissions (SMOKE) tool which generates emissions in a format for use in the Community Multiscale Air Quality (CMAQ) model. Through collaborations between UCAR and U.S. EPA, the NEI 2017 has been made available in CMAQ-ready netCDF format at 12 x 12 km² resolution over the contiguous U.S. and can be download from the UCAR NCAR/ACOM WRF-Chem webpage (<https://www2.acom.ucar.edu/wrf-chem/wrf-chem-tools-community>). The provided emissions are day and year-specific with hourly resolution. Sector specific information is available for major source categories. Chemical speciation follows the Carbon Bond mechanism version 6 (CB6). NCAR/ACOM also provides a tool which transforms the CMAQ ready files into a format for use in WRF-Chem. Since the NEI emissions have day of the week variability, we have developed a mapping to conserve the day of week when using NEI 2017 emissions for other years (e.g., 2021). In this mapping, the first Monday of 2017 is mapped to the first Monday of the target year and so on.

4.3 NO₂ and Particulate matter attribution

4.3.1 LOTOS-EUROS model

The 3-D regional chemistry transport model LOTOS-EUROS is aimed at the simulation of air pollution in the lower troposphere. Meteorological input is obtained from an off-line model, in this case from ECMWF. The model is of intermediate complexity in the sense that the relevant processes are parameterized in such a way that the computational demands are modest enabling long-term simulations within acceptable computational time. LOTOS-EUROS version 2.2 was used for the AQ-WATCH forecasts. For a more detailed model description more details of the model please refer to Manders et al. (2017) and the website www.lotos-euros.tno.nl.

The model is a Eulerian grid model, which means that the calculations are performed on a fixed three-dimensional grid. On this grid the concentration changes due to advection, vertical mixing, chemical transformations and removal by wet and dry deposition are performed. For the chemistry schemes, the model adopts the CBM4 scheme for calculation of gas-phase chemistry (Gery et al., 1989). For secondary inorganic chemistry Isorropia II (Fountoukis and Nenes, 2007) is used and heterogeneous chemistry on wet aerosol surface (R.J. Wichink Kruit et al., 2012). In cloud oxidation process are described in a pH-dependent cloud chemistry scheme (Banzhaf et al., 2012). Land use information is obtained from the Global Land Cover (GLC) 2000 database (<http://forobs.jrc.ec.europa.eu/products/glc2000/glc2000.php>). Boundary layer height taken from input meteorology from ECMWF.

For dry deposition, a resistance approach is used, as implemented in the DEPAC (DEPosition of Acidifying Compounds) module (Van Zanten et al., 2010). Furthermore, a compensation point approach for ammonia is included in the dry deposition module (R. J. Wichink Kruit et al., 2012). The deposition scheme by Zhang (2001) is used for particles, explicitly including particle size and sedimentation. The wet deposition module considers in/below-cloud scavenging and accounts for droplet saturation (Banzhaf et al., 2012).

The process calculations require information about anthropogenic emissions and meteorological conditions, which must be prescribed to the model system. For anthropogenic emission in the operational service, the CAMS-GLOB-ANT v4.2 is used (Granier et al., 2019) (see section 4.2.1). Dust and aerosol emissions are calculated online. The MEGANv2 dataset is adopted for biogenic emissions (Guenther et al., 2012) and the GFAS wild fire product is used for biomass burning (Kaiser et al., 2012). Diurnal and weekly profiles are applied to the emission data by sector. Note that these time profiles originate from European studies and may not be fully representative for the two targeted regions within AQ-watch. Previous forecast results are adopted for the initial conditions of forecast runs, while ECMWF Composition-IFS data are used as the boundary conditions (Flemming et al., 2015). The system also uses the operational streams to C-IFS products for meteorology.

4.3.2 Source attribution method in LOTOS-EUROS

The source attribution system within LOTOS-EUROS is based on a labelling technique (Kranenburg et al., 2013), which follows emitted components through the model system. With

this system the contributions from different source categories or regions (e.g. countries) are calculated. The categories and regions are flexible and can be defined according to the user needs. The system is currently targeting both primary, inert aerosol tracers as well as chemically active tracers containing a C, N (reduced and oxidized) or S atom, as these are conserved and traceable. With the method a source attribution is provided which is valid for current atmospheric conditions because all chemical conversions occur under the same oxidant levels. The source apportionment system in LOTOS-EUROS has been applied in several studies to investigate the sources of PM (Hendriks et al., 2013; Timmermans et al., 2017) and NO₂ (Schaap et al., 2013). The system also runs operationally over Europe, and results can be viewed through the website: <https://topas.tno.nl/>.

The contributions for secondary aerosols that consist of two components (such as ammonium nitrate (NH₄NO₃)) are determined by attributing half of the mass to each component source. For instance for ammonium nitrate the mass is attributed evenly (50%) to the source of ammonium (predominantly NH₃ from the agricultural sector) and to the source of nitrate (for example NO₂ from the transport sector). The underlying reason for this choice is that to produce the combined secondary aerosol both components and sources are needed.

4.3.3 System set-up

For the target region in Colorado Northern Front Range in the US, two domains (see Figure 3 left plot) are set up through a one-way nesting procedure, with the horizontal resolutions of the outer domain (25° - 50°N ´ 80° - 120° W) and inner domain (36° - 42° N × 110° - 101° W) being 0.5° × 0.25° (or 36/50 km × 28 km) and 0.1° × 0.05° (or 8 km × 6 km) respectively, and with 12 levels vertically. For the target region of Santiago de Chile in South America (see Figure 3 right plot) three domains are set up through a one-way nesting procedure, with the horizontal resolutions of the outermost to the innermost inner domain (35° - 32° S × 72° - 69° W) equal to 0.5° × 0.25° (or 33/54 km × 28 km), 0.25° × 0.125° (or 21/26 km × 14 km) and 0.05° × 0.025° (or 3 km × 3 km) respectively, and with 12 levels vertically.

Figure 3: The two North American domains with zoom over Colorado Northern Front Range (left) and three South American domains with zoom over South America, Chile and Santiago (right) of the LOTOS-EUROS-TNO model

Two different source attributions simulations are performed with an aim on sector and geographical attribution. For the sector attribution the tags for the North American domain were chosen in accordance with knowledge on the main contributors to NO_2 and PM in this region. Within the source sectors the coal and biomass fuels have been tagged separately. The sector contributions are tracked for sources located within and outside of Colorado. In addition, three natural sources (sea salt, dust and wildfires) are tracked separately. For the geographical attribution we have chosen Colorado as state as well as surrounding states separately. The emissions of all other states are tracked together with a single tag. A separate tag is used for sources from outside the US (Intercontinental). This tagging set-up is flexible and may be changed based on user consultations.

The tags on source sectors for the North American domain are chosen in accordance with knowledge on the main contributors to NO_2 and PM in this region. Within the source sectors the coal and biomass fuels have been tagged separately. The sector speciation is available for sources within and outside of Colorado. In addition, the natural sources (dust and sea salt), dust separately and wildfires, are tracked separately. For the source regions we have chosen Colorado as state as well as surrounding states separately. All other states are merged. A

separate tag is used for sources from outside the US (Intercontinental). This tagging set-up is flexible and may be changed based on user consultations.

Figure 4: Tagging set-up for the geographical and sector-oriented source attribution for Colorado

The tags on source sectors for the South American domain are chosen in accordance with knowledge on the main contributors to NO₂ and PM in this region. Within the source sectors the coal and biomass fuels have been tagged separately. The sector speciation is available for all sources within Santiago de Chile, Chile and outside of Chile. In addition, the natural sources dust, marine (sea salt) and wildfires, are tracked separately. For the source regions we have chosen Colorado as state as well as surrounding states separately. All other states are merged. A separate tag is used for sources from outside the US (Intercontinental). This tagging set-up is flexible and may be changed based on user consultations.

Figure 5: Tagging set-up for the South American domain

4.3.4 Evaluation

A first step in evaluating the calculated source contributions is to evaluate whether the modelled NO_2 and PM concentrations are in line with concentrations from observations. Large gaps between modelled and observed concentrations could indicate missing or under- or overestimated sources and therefore influence the source attributions. Such gaps then require proper analysis of potential causes to accompany the source contribution estimates.

To be able to provide a proper evaluation, we decided to focus the evaluation on a period in the past for which a reasonable number of observations are available, and which fits the available emission information. To investigate the performance under different meteorological conditions we have chosen a summer month and a winter month. The test period of January 2016 corresponds to a winter month in North America and summer month in South America, and the test period of July 2016 corresponds to a summer month in North America and winter month in South America.

In the evaluation we include the basic statistical quantities: bias, root mean square error and correlation coefficient.

For the evaluation of the LOTOS-EUROS simulations over the US and Colorado, we are using ground-based observations of from the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency's (EPA) Air Quality System (AQS) (see <https://www.epa.gov/aqs>). Evaluation over Chile has been performed using ground-based observation data from the monitoring networks of the Chilean Ministry of Environment, which are provided by the project partners from the university of Chile.

4.3.4.1 South American domain

For the domain focusing on Santiago de Chile, an initial evaluation from test runs using the CAMS-GLOB-ANT v4.2 emissions showed that the model on average only calculated around 1/3 of the observed PM_{2.5} concentrations. Huneus et al. (2020) showed that an emission inventory based on local Chilean emission information showed large differences with the CAMS-GLOB-ANT v4.2 emissions. This is also illustrated in Figure 2. For this reason, new model runs have been performed including local information on the residential combustion emissions. Note this is not yet the full set as described in Section 0 (which will be tested in the near future), but only local information for this one sector.

Including the local emission information for residential combustion considerably improves the model performance over Santiago de Chile (see Figure 6). NO₂ in the summer month January shows a nice comparison, for most stations for the zoom run at highest resolution around Santiago de Chile. For the winter month July the comparison is showing scattered results. The PM_{2.5} concentrations do not show the underestimation that was previously seen with the CAMS-GLOB-ANT v4.2 emissions and especially in summer the modeled values are now close to observed values. However, the PM₁₀ concentrations in summer are still underestimated and in winter there is a group of stations which is quite well represented while for another set of stations the PM concentrations are overestimated.

The large scatter seen in the results for both NO₂ and PM may be caused by errors in the meteorological input of the model. The complex surrounding topography has a strong influence on the air pollution and its variations in Santiago de Chile and resolving especially the wind speed conditions in winter is difficult as was also highlighted by Saide et al. (2016). The resolution of the ECMWF meteorology (10 km) used within the model runs is not expected to be representative of the actual meteorology, especially regarding windspeed and direction. Indeed in Figure 7, it can be seen that the variability in observed wind speeds in winter is not captured by the ECMWF meteorology. Also, the wind direction from ECMWF shows large differences with observed values. To be able to represent this better, high resolution meteorological input data would be needed. It is therefore recommended to replace the ECMWF meteorology with high resolution WRF meteorology for better performance of the service in this region with large orographic variations.

Figure 6: Comparison between the monthly averaged modelled and observed concentrations for the Santiago de Chile domain for NO₂ (top row), PM_{2.5} (second row) and PM₁₀ (bottom row) for the study months January 2016 (left) and July 2016 (right).

Figure 7: Comparison of windspeed from ECMWF versus observed windspeeds in January 2016 (left) and July 2016 (right)

Figure 8: Comparison of wind direction from ECMWF versus observed wind direction in January 2016 (left) and July 2016 (right)

Recently an update of the Chilean emissions has been made available in combination with CAMS global emissions (see section 0) and new test runs with these updated emissions for more source sectors are also planned in the coming period.

Note these emissions have not been included yet in the operational model set-up which is still using the CAMS-GLOB-ANT v4.2.

4.3.4.2 North American domain

As seen above for South America, the inclusion of local information on emissions can considerably improve the model performance. For the North American domain, we have not yet implemented the local NEI emissions (section 4.2.4) and runs are performed with the CAMS-GLOB-Ant v4.2 emissions.

Figure 9 shows the comparison between the modelled and observed concentrations of monthly mean surface concentration of NO₂ and PM_{2.5} for stations in the Colorado Front Range domain, from the zoom run at ~6 to 8km resolution. An underestimation of NO₂ concentrations is seen, especially at locations with larger mean concentrations, which can be partly attributed to the resolution of the model, not representing observed values at stations near traffic roads. But we also see that NEI attributes larger share of the NO_x emissions to urban areas, including the Denver area, than the applied CAMS-GLOB-Ant v4.2 inventory (see Figure 11). The five stations with highest observed NO₂ concentrations are located in Denver, so the use of the NEI

emissions is foreseen to increase the concentrations for these stations and thereby improve the comparison. For stations which can be more characterized as urban background the comparison shows the model is able to nicely represent the variations observed in NO₂, as can be seen in the example in Cheyenne (Figure 10), which is located to the North of Denver at the boundary of our Colorado domain.

Figure 9: Comparison between the modelled and AQS observed concentrations of NO₂ (left panels) and PM_{2.5} (right panels) in the test period of January (top) and July (bottom) 2016.

Figure 10: Timeseries of NO₂ for the station in Cheyenne, located in an urban background area for January 2016 from LOTOS-EUROS (green line) and AQS observations (black dots).

Figure 11: Relative difference between NEI emissions and CAMS-GLOB-ANT v4.2 ($(\text{NEI}-\text{CAMS})/\text{CAMS}$) for NO_x January 2017 (left plot) and NH₃ July 2017 (right plot). The green areas mostly correspond to areas where the emissions are very low.

We also found an overestimation of ozone in summer (not shown here), which is commonly seen in global and regional models over the US. (e.g. Fiore et al., 2014; Guo et al., 2018). One of the possible reasons for this is an overestimation of biogenic NMVOC emissions and with this of the production of ozone in summer. In the model we use an older version of MEGAN to estimate the BVOC emissions. As a sensitivity test, we plan to perform an additional model run using the CAMS-GLOB-BIO v2.2 global biogenic emissions inventory.

The PM_{2.5} concentrations are also underestimated by the model. This is partly related to the underestimation of the NO₂, which acts as a precursor of PM. The same holds for another precursor, NH₃, which might also be underestimated by the model and where again NEI shows much larger emissions over agricultural areas, which are often located to nearby large cities as well (Figure 11 right plot).

A first comparison of top-down estimates of NH₃ emissions from the CrIs satellite shows much larger ammonia emissions across the US than included in the CAMS-GLOB-ANT v4.2 (Figure 12), similar to what was found in Cao et al. (2020) in an comparison with NEI 2008 emissions. In the last year of the project, we will further investigate whether and how NH₃ emission distribution and timing should be improved through comparisons with both ground-based and satellite observations.

Figure 12: Comparison of satellite estimate of NH₃ emissions versus CAMS-GLOB-ANT v4.2 NH₃ emissions (Dammers et al., 2022 under preparation)

Additionally, evaluation of the model performance over the larger Northern-America domain (not shown here) illustrates a large range of variation in the performance. For stations located near arid regions large PM biases are present. The dust production within the domain in LOTOS-EUROS is dependent on the land use type. Further investigation showed that many of the arid regions are classified in our land use map as open-closed shrubs, which in our current set-up does not allow any wind-blown dust emissions. A new set-up allowing dust production over this land use type was tested and shows a large increase of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ concentrations at specific times over the Colorado region.

At stations that are less influenced by dust the model performance is better. It is therefore recommended to improve the land use map and implementation of the dust emission to better represent this important source of PM.

Finally the exclusion of secondary organic aerosol (SOA) production in the current model set-up will also lead to an underestimation of PM_{2.5}, however the SOA contribution to PM_{2.5} is estimated to be small in the region of Colorado (Pye et al., 2021).

4.3.5 Attribution results

The operational service provides a daily source attribution of NO₂ and PM for the past 6 weeks. Below an example is given for the period of December 2020 up to 8th of January 2021. In Colorado where this corresponds to a winter month, the dominant contribution comes from residential combustion. But there are some days, where also traffic, industry and power plants have large contributions. Note that it is recommended above to include regional emission information to improve the model performance, which will also impact these contributions. For Santiago de Chile also, residential combustion has a considerable contribution, but here on most days there are also large contributions from traffic, industry and natural sources (sea salt and dust).

The contribution from agriculture at both locations in these plots is small. However as presented above, there are suggestions based on comparisons of the NH₃ emissions with estimate from satellites that the CAMS-GLOB-ANT emissions from agriculture may be underestimated.

Figure 13: Examples of 6 weeks source sector attribution of PM10 for a station in Santiago de Chile (top plot) and a station in the Colorado Front Range (Broadway, bottom plot)

4.4 CO attribution

4.4.1 WRF-CHEM model

The Weather Research and Forecasting model with Chemistry (WRF-Chem) is a publicly available community model (Grell et al., 2005; Powers et al., 2017). The chemistry component of WRF-Chem is fully consistent with the meteorological component; both components use the same transport scheme (mass and scalar preserving), the same horizontal and vertical grids, the same physical schemes for sub grid-scale transport, and the same time step for transport and vertical mixing.

UCAR is the main developer of the WRF model and a major contributor to WRF-Chem (<https://www2.acom.ucar.edu/wrf-chem>). WRF-Chem is a fully coupled regional chemical transport model which offers a wide range of chemical and physical options. Based on WRF-Chem V3.9.1, UCAR has setup a regional forecast system over the contiguous U.S. (CONUS) at 12 km x 12 km which has been in operation since May 2019. A second forecast system based on WRF-Chem V4.1 for AQ-WATCH has been added in June 2020 (Section 4.4.3). The forecast products and near-real time evaluation results are visualized on a dissemination website (<https://www.acom.ucar.edu/firex-aq/forecast.shtml>). These forecasts serve as input to the AQ-WATCH attribution and mitigation service.

4.4.2 Source attribution method in WRF-CHEM

In the model setup, six CO tracers are setup that are used to track (1) CO emitted from anthropogenic and (2) biomass burning emissions inside the model domain, (3) CO produced from the photochemical oxidation of VOCs, (4) background CO generated from the sources located outside of the contiguous US (CONUS) and (5) for sources in Asia only, and (6) background CO generated from fires outside of CONUS. Information on the non-CONUS tracers is taken from the WACCM model. These tracers do not affect the model physics or chemistry but undergo all model processes (Kumar et al., 2021). Key meteorological parameters, air pollutants and CO tracers are displayed on the UCAR dissemination forecast webpage.

4.4.3 System set-up

The configuration for the AQ-WATCH forecast setup which has been running in parallel to the standard setup since June 2020 covers the contiguous U.S. at 12 km x 12 km and Colorado at 4 km x 4 km. Gas-phase chemistry is simulated with the T1 MOZART scheme (Emmons et al., 2020) that is coupled to the Goddard Global Ozone Chemistry Aerosol Radiation and Transport (GOCART) aerosol scheme (Chin et al., 2000; Ginoux et al., 2001). For more details on the overall model setup we refer to <https://www.acom.ucar.edu/firex-aq/tracers.shtml> and to Kumar et al. (2021). The boundary layer is simulated using the YSU scheme and land use information is provided by MODIS products (<https://lpdaac.usgs.gov>). A resistance-based approach is adopted to simulate dry deposition (Wesely, 1989), while in-cloud and below-cloud scavenging is included for wet deposition (Neu and Prather, 2012).

The WRF-Chem-UCAR model forecasts are initialized daily and forced at the lateral boundaries by 3-hourly meteorological analysis data from the NCEP Global Forecast System (GFS) at 0.25° resolution (<https://rda.ucar.edu/datasets/ds084.1/>). For anthropogenic emissions, the National

Emission Inventory (NEI) 2017 at a 12 km resolution is used for the AQ-WATCH setup (<https://www.epa.gov/air-emissions-inventories/2017-national-emissions-inventory-nei-data>), which is regridded to the model resolution using a mass conserving mapping. Day of week mapping from the NEI representative year to the target year is applied to the emission data, and diurnal variations are included for all sectors. For the other emission inputs, the GOCART module is adopted for inline calculation of the emissions of dust and sea-salt aerosols (Chin et al., 2000; Ginoux et al., 2001), MEGANv2 for biogenic emissions (Guenther et al., 2012), and FINNv1 for biomass burning (Wiedinmyer et al., 2011). The latter is subject to an online plume rise parametrization (Freitas et al., 2007). Dynamic 6-hourly outputs from the Whole Atmosphere Community Climate Model (WACCM) from UCAR's forecast system (<https://www.acom.ucar.edu/waccm/forecast/>) are adopted as the boundary conditions of chemical variables. WACCM simulations also provide oxygen and ozone column densities also used for photolysis calculations (Marsh et al., 2013). Figure 14 provides a schematic of the forecast system. Forecasts are issued daily for the next 2 days.

Figure 14: Architecture of the UCAR air quality forecasting system (from Kumar et al., 2021)

4.4.4 Evaluation

The forecasts are undergoing near-real-time evaluation with surface observations of ozone and PM_{2.5} from the U.S. EPA AIRNOW network. The data typically become available 3 hours past current time, but new data availability is checked until 2 days before present since sometimes the AIRNOW system experiences delayed data delivery for some sites. Surface observations are displayed on the forecast maps and in addition we also provide evaluation statistics including time series and spatial correlation and bias. For these, the model output is paired with the location and time of the in-situ observations through bilinear interpolation to the observation site locations. This evaluation is performed in 10 regions defined by the EPA as well as for the State of Colorado and the Colorado Front Range. Model performance is evaluated separately for the first and second days of the forecast to assess variations in the model performance as a function of the lead time. Performance of meteorology and surface PM_{2.5} for June 2019-May 2020 is also discussed in (Kumar et al., 2021). This study showed that the system has excellent skill in capturing hourly to daily variations in temperature, surface pressure, relative humidity, water vapor mixing ratios, and wind direction but shows relatively larger errors in wind speed. The model also captures the seasonal cycle of surface PM_{2.5} very well in different regions and for different types of sites (urban, suburban, and rural) in the CONUS with a mean bias smaller

than $1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ (Kumar et al., 2021). The skill of the air quality forecasts was found to remain fairly stable between the first and second days of the forecasts.

We have also used the MOPITT version 8 Level 2 retrieval product to evaluate modelled distribution of CO. The MOPITT instrument on board the Terra satellite is a part of National Aeronautics and Space Administration's (NASA) Earth Observing System (EOS). Information regarding MOPITT v8 data can be found at https://www2.acom.ucar.edu/sites/default/files/mopitt/v8_users_guide_201812.pdf and product validation is discussed in (Deeter et al., 2019). For this study, we have only chosen clear sky retrievals with signal to noise ratio exceeding 1000 and solar zenith angle less than 80 degrees. The filtered daily retrievals are then compared with WRF simulated CO. Before comparison, WRF simulated CO profiles and total CO columns are convolved with MOPITT averaging kernel and a priori profiles. This convolution transforms the model CO profile into one that will be seen by MOPITT in the absence of other errors.

Figure 15: Comparison of the vertical distribution of MOPITT CO profiles against WRF-Chem CO profiles averaged over the CONUS during August 2019. WRF (orig) shows the raw vertical CO profile simulated by WRF-Chem and WRF (AK) shows the WRF-Chem CO vertical profile convolved with MOPITT a priori profile and averaging kernels. “MOP Apr” and “MOP Ret” represent the MOPITT a priori and retrieved profiles, respectively. Right panel: Vertical profiles of MOPITT averaging kernels corresponding to different pressure levels that are used in convolving the raw WRF-Chem CO profiles.

Figure 15 compares the vertical distribution of MOPITT CO profiles (“MOP Ret”) against convolved WRF-Chem CO profiles (“WRF (AK)”) averaged over the CONUS during August 2019. Monthly averaged MOPITT a priori (“MOP Apr”) and the raw WRF-Chem simulated CO profiles (“WRF (Orig)”) are also shown for the comparison. Monthly averaged averaging kernel profiles corresponding to different pressure levels are also shown to depict the sensitivity of MOPITT to atmospheric CO over the CONUS. Averaging kernel profiles show that MOPITT retrievals contain 1-2 pieces of independent information with the profiles for 600-1000 hPa peaking in the lower troposphere and those for 200-600 hPa peaking in the upper troposphere. The WRF-Chem captures the variations in the vertical profiles of MOPITT retrieved CO with higher values near the surface and a secondary peak in the upper troposphere but underestimates the MOPITT retrieved CO profiles throughout the troposphere. The uncertainties in modelled CO arise from several factors including uncertainties in the emissions, chemistry, and transport. While it is

difficult to pinpoint the sources of uncertainties in our simulations, CO source contribution analysis (Figure 19) indicates that CO budget in the model is primarily controlled by the anthropogenic emissions, fire emissions, and inflow from the domain boundaries. This suggests that anthropogenic and fire emissions and boundary conditions from the global model are likely the main sources of uncertainties in our simulations. It is well known that global models including CAM-chem (which represent the tropospheric chemistry in WACCM) significantly underestimate tropospheric CO (Emmons et al., 2020). CAM-chem has a bias of about -40% against both surface and MOPITT CO in the northern hemisphere which is attributed mainly to underestimation of anthropogenic emissions (Emmons et al., 2020; Gaubert et al., 2017). Thus, some of the underestimation can be attributed to errors in inflow of CO into our model domain. Furthermore, the fire emissions in our set-up are represented using FINN v1, which uses the MODIS retrieved active fire locations to identify biomass burning regions. A recent study focused on sub-Saharan Africa suggested that the resolution of MODIS is too coarse to capture small scale fires and consequently MODIS burned area estimate can be lower by 80% compared to the burned area estimated with 20-m resolution of Sentinel-2 multispectral instrument (Ramo et al., 2021). The underestimation of biomass burning emissions is common across all available biomass burning emission inventories as found in a comparison of MOPITT total column CO against an ensemble of CAM-chem simulations driven by different top-down and bottom-up biomass burning emission inventories in 2014.

In addition to the above, the system also provides dedicated forecasts and evaluation for the NASA Tropospheric Ozone Lidar Network (TOLNET) (<https://www.acom.ucar.edu/tolnet/station.shtml>) as well as comparison to TROPOMI NO₂ (<https://www.acom.ucar.edu/satellite/forecast.shtml>).

Offline comparisons are also conducted for selected time periods such as during large wildfire impacts. As an example, we show in Figure 16 a comparison of WRF-Chem AOD with MODIS derived AOD for 16 September 2020. The model fairly well represents the satellite derived AOD and the CO CONUS fire tracer, which is also shown and provides information on the CO attributed to fires within CONUS, suggests that the high aerosol concentrations are related to wildfires within CONUS.

Figure 16: MODIS AOD (left), WRF-Chem AOD (middle) and CO CONUS fire tracer for 16 September 2020.

4.4.5 Attribution results

Here we provide examples to give an overview of the value of the CO tracers. The fire tracers specifically have shown to be of great value to the scientist community and the prime users. Figure 17 shows results for a wildfire impacted period demonstrating the value of the CO tracers in determining the origin of the smoke impact during August 2021. The maps shown are taken from the UCAR dissemination webpage.

Figure 17: Maps showing the transport of CO from fires within CONUS (left) and outside CONUS (middle) and how it led to very high surface PM2.5 on 6 August 2021 (right). The Western half of the U.S. was mostly impacted by the U.S. fires while fires in Canada mostly impacted the NE U.S. Impacts from agricultural burning in the SE U.S. is also evident.

The CO tracers are also used to look more closely into the 2020 wildfire season in Colorado, which was among the worst reported in history, and its impact on surface ozone. Figure 18 shows an example for 20-26 August 2020 when local fires as well as transported smoke impacted the Front Range. Although this figure shows only one time step a similar tendency was observed during other times and high ozone levels are seen at several surface sites already early morning suggesting that ozone from remote fires was transported into the region.

Figure 18: Spatial distribution of MODIS TERRA aerosol optical depth (AOD) (left panel), CO CONUS fire tracer (second from left), surface ozone mixing ratio (third from the left), and HYSPLIT back air trajectory initiated from 12 NCFR sites during Aug 20th to Aug 26th 2020 (top to bottom)

Figure 19 shows the spatial distribution of surface layer CO mixing ratios (panel [a]) along with percentage contributions of anthropogenic emissions from Colorado (panel [b]), inflow of CO from non-Colorado emission sources into Colorado (panel [c]), fire emissions in Colorado

(panel[d]), transport of CO from Asia (panel [e]), and photochemical production of CO from oxidation of VOCs emitted in Colorado (panel [f]). These results are based on an average of 48-h forecast launched on 23 Nov 2021 00 UTC. In this case, the highest CO mixing ratios at the surface are seen in the Denver Metro area followed by the northern Colorado Front Range. The spatial distributions of different source contribution terms show dominance of anthropogenic emissions and non-Colorado emission sources in controlling surface CO distribution over Colorado. Anthropogenic emissions dominate in urban/sub-urban areas of Colorado while the non-Colorado emission sources dominate in rural/mountainous regions. The contribution of CO-Asia is in the range of 15-30% that highlights the importance of long-range transport of air pollutants on local air quality in Colorado. Analysis of the non-US fire CO tracer (not shown in Figure 19) showed that fires outside US contributed less than 10% to surface CO for this forecast cycle. The contribution of fires within Colorado and photochemical production from oxidation of VOCs is also small.

Figure 19: An example of source attribution analysis of CO over Colorado, USA. Spatial distribution of surface layer CO mixing ratios averaged over 48-h of the forecast cycle launched on 23 Nov 2011 are shown. The contributions of different sources are shown in panels [b]-[f]. Note that CO Asia is also a fraction of CO Non-Colorado.

4.5 Next steps and recommendations

4.5.1 Use of national emission inventories

The use of regional emission inventories is recommended as showed in the results for the NO₂ and PM service with the LOTOS-EUROS model. In the last year of the project, we will aim to include the NEI and INEMA emissions in the LOTOS-EUROS model for the PM and NO₂ attribution service over Colorado and Santiago de Chile, respectively.

For Chile additional sources of information will be explored to included currently missing CH₄ emissions in the energy and industry sector. Additionally, the VOC emissions in the energy and industry sectors will be specified to address the assumptions made regarding VOC emissions in these sectors.

4.5.2 Extensions of the service

UCAR plans to hold a meeting with the prime user in Colorado (CDPHE) for early 2022 where the latest version of the AQ-WATCH attribution tool will be presented to them. Dependent on the prime user feedback and their needs additional CO tracers might be included. Upon request of CDPHE we already had early in the project added a CO tracer for sources in Asia.

Within the LOTOS-EUROS service the extension to SO₂ and health impact indicators will be considered.

4.5.3 Evaluation of source attribution

In the report we shared some results of the evaluation of modelled concentrations, however also the calculated source attributions can be evaluated with tracers which are specific for certain emission sources (e.g. V/Ni, Levoglucosan, BC, etc.). We will investigate the availability of these tracer observations for an evaluation of the service with these tracers.

4.5.4 Role of agriculture

Special attention will be given to the role of agricultural emissions. We will try to evaluate and improve the emission information through the use NH₃ observations from satellites and information from crop maps. Figure 20 shows a first comparison of CAMS-GLOB-ANT emissions with estimates derived from the CrIS satellite. Where the comparison is good over Europe. For the US and Canada, the CrIS estimates are a factor 2-3 higher than in the CAMS inventory. These results will be reported in the updated version of this document.

Figure 20: Comparison of CrIS satellite estimate of NH₃ emissions versus CAMS-GLOB-ANT v4.2 NH₃ emissions for Europe (left plot) and the US/Canada (right plot) (Dammers et al., 2022 under preparation)

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6 Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is

X	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This report is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

6.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

- The latest version of the service will be presented to the prime users in Colorado and Chile in early 2022.
- The service will also be presented at several public events (e.g. the air quality conference, LOTOS-EUROS workshops)

7 Deliverable timeliness

Is the deliverable delayed?

Yes No

Justification: The development of the source attribution tool interface was delayed. Additional time was necessary to obtain the screenshots of the latest version of the interface for the completeness of this deliverable.

8 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

The evaluation for the new PM, NO₂ service over Chile and Colorado showed a strong need for improvements in the model inputs using local information, such as emissions. This is required for achieving a good performance of modelled concentrations and with that of source contributions. The implementation of such new inputs requires considerable effort and expected uncertainties in the emissions currently still prevents a proper assessment of the role of agriculture. The results with the improved implementation will be reported in the updated version of this document.

9 Sustainability

9.1 Lessons learnt: both positive and negative that can be drawn from the experiences of the work to date

The set-up of the service in Santiago de Chile and Colorado for PM and NO₂ with the LOTOS-EUROS model which is usually applied over Europe has provided lessons which can be used for application to new regions/clients.

9.2 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

The source attribution service is based on the air quality forecasts developed within WP3. It serves as basis for the mitigation service, which will be described in Deliverable D4.2 (Report with description of mitigation service)

10 Full track of dissemination activities

Type of dissemination and communication activities	Details	Location , dates	Audience	Link in website (if applicable)	Estimated number of persons reached
Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)	<p>Launch of report on air pollution in Central and Southern Chile. Chilean Minister of Energy participated in the launch of the Report:</p> <p>Huneus, N., et al., El aire que respiramos: pasado, presente y futuro – Contaminación atmosférica por MP2,5 en el centro y sur de Chile (The air we breathe: past, present and future - Air pollution by PM2.5 in central and southern Chile)</p> <p>Report of the Centre for Climate and Resilience Research</p>	September 7th, 2020	General public and decision makers	https://www.cr2.cl/contaminacion/	~200 at launch event and it has been downloaded multiple time since it was launched

11 Full track of publications and IP

11.1 Peer reviewed articles

Article in Journal:

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-2021-216>

Álamos, N., Huneus, N., Opazo, M., Osses, M., Puja, S., Pantoja, N., Denier van der Gon, H., Schueftan, A., Reyes, R., and Calvo, R., High resolution inventory of atmospheric emissions from transport, industrial, energy, mining and residential sectors of Chile, Earth Syst. Sci. Data, discussion paper, 2021

11.2 Publications in preparation OR submitted:

Not applicable

11.3 Intellectual property rights resulting from this deliverable:

Not applicable